

Grant Agreement N° 101188256

**Deliverable D1.2
Data Management Plan**

Contractual delivery date: M6
 Actual delivery date: 30.06.2025
 Responsible partner: P1 - SRL, Norway

Project Title	Horizon Europe EOSC FAIR2Adapt project
Deliverable number	D1.2
Deliverable title	Data Management Plan
Author(s):	Louise Bolands Eklund (SRL), Anne Fouilloux (SRL)
Responsible Partner:	P1 - SRL
Date:	5.03.2025
Nature	R
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

Work package number	WP1 - Project Management, Coordination, and Governance
Work package leader	SRL, Norway
Abstract:	The Data Management Plan will evolve during the lifetime of the project in order to present the status of the project's reflections on data management. Our DMP will be made publicly available on ROHub so that the up to date version can be consulted at any time by everyone.
Keyword List:	data management, coordination, governance.

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon Europe Work Programme (HE) under grant agreement no 101188256.

This report reflects the views only of the authors and does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible or liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Editor(s):	Louise Bolands Eklund (SRL), Anne Fouilloux (SRL)
Reviewer(s):	Esteban Gonzales (UPM), Barbara Magagna (GFF)
Internally approved by:	Anne Fouilloux (SRL)
Recommended/mandatory readers:	All WPs

Document Description

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

V0.1	25.03.2025	First draft version	Louise Bolands Eklund (SRL), Anne Fouilloux (SRL)
V0.2	13.06.2025	Updated version based on the initial collection of data management requirements from the partners.	Anne Fouilloux (SRL)
V0.3	15.06.2025	Review the deliverable.	Barbara Magagna (GFF)
V0.4	27.06.2025	Review the deliverable and include a section about “other research outputs”.	Esteban Gonzales (UPM)
V.1.0	30.06.2025	Final review and consolidation of D1.2	Louise Bolands Eklund (SRL), Anne Fouilloux (SRL)

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
1.1. Scope	6
1.2. Audience	8
1.3. Structure	8
2. Data Summary and initial datasets	10
2.1. Data Re-use Strategy and Rationale	11
2.2. Case Study 1: Arctic radioisotopes	15
2.3. Case Study 2: Biscayan RiOMar	17
2.4. Case Study 3: City of Hamburg	19
2.5. Case Study 4: Designing a FAIR national adaptation hub	22
2.6. Case Study 5: Enriching weADAPT and the connectivity hub global	29
2.7. Case Study 6: FAIR Climate risk data for businesses	32
2.8. Transfer cases	36
2.9. Communication and Training Data	37
2.10. Data Utility Beyond FAIR2Adapt	37
2.11. Comprehensive Data Overview	38
3. Other Research Outputs	41
4. FAIR data	45

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	45
4.2. Making data accessible	47
4.3. Making data interoperable	49
4.4. Increase data re-use	53
5. Allocation of resources	57
6. Security and Ethics considerations	59
7. Annex	61

Terms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
API	Application Programming Interface
ARCO	Analysis Ready Cloud Optimised data format
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GEMET	GEneral Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus
IPMA	Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere
MOOSE	Mediterranean Ocean Observing System for the Environment
NorESM	Norwegian Earth System Model
OAF	OGC API Feature

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
API	Application Programming Interface
ARCO	Analysis Ready Cloud Optimised data format
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DMP	Data Management Plan
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OSF	Open Science Framework
PID	Persistent Identifier
PHYTOBS	French Phytoplankton observation network
PSNC	Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure
RO	Research Object
STA	Sensor Thing API
TCFD	Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures
W3ID	World Wide Web Identifier
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Mapping Service

Executive Summary

FAIR2Adapt enhances climate resilience by making climate data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), enabling policymakers and researchers to develop evidence-based adaptation strategies across Europe.

This document serves as the **Data Management Plan** for the **FAIR2Adapt** project.

Make sure to select headings in the sidebar to see a table of contents.

1. Introduction

FAIR2Adapt is a European initiative aimed at increasing climate resilience by enhancing the availability and usability of climate data for adaptation planning. Through the application of FAIR principles, the project enables climate-related data to be more accessible, interoperable, and reusable, supporting the development of robust adaptation strategies across Europe.

The purpose of this Data Management Plan is to ensure that all data generated, collected, and used within the FAIR2Adapt project is managed in alignment with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. This plan outlines the strategies and protocols for data storage, accessibility, sharing, and long-term preservation to maximize the usability and impact of climate-related data for adaptation planning. By defining clear guidelines for metadata standards, licensing, and interoperability, the plan facilitates seamless integration with existing climate data infrastructures, supports compliance with open science policies, and enhances collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders.

1.1. Scope

Effective data management is a cornerstone of responsible and impactful research, particularly in projects aiming to support societal resilience to climate change. The FAIR2Adapt project, funded under the Horizon 2020 INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 call, is

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

committed to advancing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and fostering open, standards-based data sharing to support the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. A key component in achieving this is the development and implementation of a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP), which plays a crucial role in supporting FAIR data principles and open data sharing.

The DMP outlines the lifecycle of data collected, processed, and generated during the FAIR2Adapt project, with a strong emphasis on ensuring that data outputs adhere to the FAIR principles—making data **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**. In line with the European Commission’s guidelines on Open Science and open research data, FAIR2Adapt aims to ensure that research data supporting climate adaptation efforts can be widely accessed, reused, and built upon.

Where feasible, all datasets necessary to validate findings published by the project will be made openly available. Additionally, the project is committed to applying FAIR principles to all types of data generated through its activities—including model outputs, climate indicators, socio-economic data, and knowledge outputs relevant to regional and sectoral adaptation planning.

The FAIR2Adapt DMP will address the following key aspects:

- **Procedures for data handling throughout the project and after its completion**, including systematic workflows for implementing FAIR principles at each stage of the data lifecycle;
- **Types and formats of data to be collected or generated**, ensuring data formats support FAIR principles through standardized, interoperable formats with rich metadata;
- **Standards and semantic artifacts used for data description and interoperability**, implementing established vocabularies and community-specific metadata schemas to ensure data is FAIR;
- **Access provisions, including open access mechanisms and justifications for any access restrictions**, following "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" while maintaining FAIR access through trusted repositories;
- **Strategies for long-term data preservation and curation**, ensuring sustained FAIR compliance through certified repositories, persistent identifiers, and EOSC integration;
- **Measures to safeguard sensitive or personal data, ensuring compliance with ethical and legal obligations**, including GDPR compliance through data minimization, anonymization techniques, and Privacy by Design approaches while maintaining FAIR principles, plus adherence to CARE principles for Indigenous and community data.

D1.2 – Data Management Plan

FAIR2Adapt will fully comply with the Horizon 2020 Grant Agreement's requirements concerning open access to research data. Data and any supporting tools or documentation needed to validate results will be deposited in trusted repositories, aligned with EOSC services, and made accessible to external users. This openness facilitates not only reproducibility but also the integration of FAIR2Adapt results into broader climate knowledge systems.

In recognition that certain data may require restricted access—for example, due to confidentiality, security, or potential misuse—the project will follow the principle of “**as open as possible, as closed as necessary.**” Any deviations from full openness will be documented transparently in the DMP, along with their justification.

This document constitutes the initial version of the FAIR2Adapt DMP and follows the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP template. The DMP will evolve throughout the project's lifetime to reflect the current status of the project's data management practices. To ensure transparency and accessibility, the DMP questionnaire is maintained using the FAIR Wizard, with ROHub providing access to the latest version. Our living DMP is publicly available on ROHub, where the most up-to-date version can be accessed at any time:

<https://w3id.org/ro-id/5954ce8e-2bbc-469a-b5ba-0d4d1e93195f>.

Snapshots are regularly archived on Zenodo, each assigned a unique DOI. They are also accessible via ROHub and contain versioned records of the DMP questionnaire and this deliverable.

1.2. Audience

The intended audience for this document includes all partners within the FAIR2Adapt consortium, as well as external stakeholders who may be involved in project oversight, communication, or reporting (e.g., European Commission representatives, advisory board).

1.3. Structure

The document is structured into several sections to provide clarity and easy navigation:

- **Data Summary and Initial Datasets:**

This section presents a general description of the initially identified datasets that will be collected, used, and produced by the FAIR2Adapt project—including datasets associated with each case study. It includes a dedicated subsection listing these datasets, serving as a reference point for monitoring progress and updates as new

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

data becomes available. It also outlines how data related to transfer cases and scaling efforts will be identified, managed, and integrated.

- **FAIR data:** This section discusses key aspects of how these datasets will be made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR).

- **Allocation of Resources:**

This section details the resources required for data management and outlines the approach to financing them, ensuring sustainable and effective handling of data throughout the project.

- **Security and Ethics Considerations:**

This part addresses issues related to data security, privacy, and ethical compliance, especially in cases involving sensitive or socio-economic data.

2. Data Summary and initial datasets

The detailed Data Management Plan (DMP) has been created using the FAIR Wizard (<https://fip.fair-wizard.com/>).

It is available from ROHub too:

<https://w3id.org/ro-id/5954ce8e-2bbc-469a-b5ba-0d4d1e93195f/resources/17181d84-f756-480f-9694-4d0b96e7a2a3>

It documents how data will be managed, FAIRified, preserved, and made accessible, ensuring transparency and long-term usability of the datasets. For the six case studies, the DMP is informed by individual FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs), each developed specifically for its respective case study.

FAIR2Adapt Community-Driven Data Management Approach

FAIR2Adapt adopts a **community-centric approach** to data management through the development of **FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)** for each of our six case studies. Each case study represents a distinct **community of practice** with specific stakeholders, data types, and use cases related to climate change adaptation. FAIR2Adapt will extensively re-use existing climate and socio-economic datasets across six case studies, with each community defining their specific FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP).

Phase 1: Community Engagement and Requirements Gathering (Months 1-12)

- **Step 1: Case Study Community Analysis**
 - Work with the six predefined case study communities established in the project proposal
 - Assess current stakeholder engagement levels and identify opportunities for involvement
 - Map existing data management practices and identify specific challenges within each case study
- **Step 2: FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) Development:** for each predefined case study community, we facilitate development of:
 - **FAIR Enabling Resources:** Standards, vocabularies, metadata schemas, and protocols
 - **FAIR Supporting Resources:** Repositories, tools, services, and platforms
 - **Community-specific practices:** Data management workflows and quality standards (*Stakeholder involvement varies by case study timing and community readiness*)

Phase 2: DMP Integration and Harmonization (Months 6-18)

- **Step 3: Integration with Overall DMP:** the FAIR2Adapt DMP aggregates and harmonizes data management practices from:
 1. **Six predefined case study communities** (via their FIPs)
 2. **Technical partners** (infrastructure and tool providers)
 3. **Cross-cutting standards** (ensuring interoperability between communities)
 4. **Communication and dissemination activities** (webinars, workshops, training materials, community feedback)

This creates a **multi-layered DMP** that respects community autonomy while ensuring technical coherence across the project.

- **Step 4: Technical Coherence Validation**
 - Identify overlaps and conflicts between community approaches
 - Develop semantic mappings and interoperability solutions
 - Ensure EOSC compliance across all community practices

Phase 3: Implementation and Iterative Refinement (Months 12-36)

Step 5: Community Validation and Testing (Months 12-24)

- Implement FIPs within each case study community
- Engage additional stakeholders as case studies progress and mature
- Collect feedback on practical usability and effectiveness
- Document lessons learned and best practices

Step 6: Transfer Case Integration (Months 18-30)

- Apply validated methodologies to newly identified transfer case communities
- Adapt FIP development process based on case study experiences
- Expand DMP to include transfer case requirements

Step 7: DMP Evolution and Sustainability (Months 24-36)

- Update DMP based on implementation experiences
- Finalize community-endorsed FAIR resources
- Establish long-term governance for continued DMP maintenance

2.1. Data Re-use Strategy and Rationale

D1.2 – Data Management Plan

FAIR2Adapt will extensively re-use existing climate and socio-economic datasets as the foundation for developing and testing our FAIRification framework for Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) communities. Rather than generating new data, the project's core mission is to understand how CCA communities currently work with data and to demonstrate how FAIR principles can enhance their existing workflows and data assets. The project's approach prioritizes leveraging existing high-quality datasets while adding value through FAIRification and enhanced interoperability.

Primary Re-use Categories

Climate Data Re-use:

- Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) outputs for Arctic scenarios;
- RiOMar model outputs from RiOMar model, a modified version of CROCO (Coastal and Regional Ocean COmmunity model) for coastal water quality assessment;
- Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) data across multiple case studies;
- National meteorological datasets from Hamburg, Portugal, and France;
- Historical climate observations from established monitoring networks.

Climate Hazard and Risk Data Re-use:

- Hamburg's Urban Data Portal flooding data and climate-induced stressor datasets
- European flood risk maps and drought indicators
- National weather extreme datasets across multiple EU member states
- Urban heat maps and heavy precipitation risk data
- Climate risk dashboards and vulnerability assessments

Marine and Coastal Data Re-use:

- JERICO-RI (European Research Infrastructure for coastal ocean observation)
- SOMLIT, MOOSE, PHYTOBS observational networks
- CoastPredict Global Ocean Observing System data
- ILICO Research Infrastructure datasets for coastal ocean observation

Socio-economic Data Re-use:

- Hamburg's Urban Data Portal containing about 572 municipal datasets
- Portuguese national statistics and demographic data
- European adaptation policy databases (Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT)
- Business climate risk datasets for EU Taxonomy compliance

Knowledge Resources Re-use:

- Existing adaptation case studies and best practices
- Policy documents and implementation guidelines
- Scientific literature and technical reports

Rationale for Re-use - Understanding and enhancing CCA communities

- **Community-Centered Approach**
 - **Understanding current practices:** We start where CCA communities are, using their existing data assets to understand their workflows, challenges, and needs;
 - **Real-world relevance:** By working with data communities actually use, we ensure our FAIRification framework addresses practical, not theoretical, problems;
 - **Stakeholder engagement:** Communities are more likely to adopt FAIR practices when applied to their familiar datasets rather than abstract examples;
- **Framework Development Goals**
 - **Testing FAIRification processes:** Existing datasets provide realistic test cases for developing robust FAIRification workflows;
 - **Demonstrating added value:** Showing how FAIR principles enhance data communities already value and use;
 - **Identifying barriers:** Understanding what prevents current datasets from being FAIR and developing solutions;
- **Avoiding Duplication and Building Trust**
 - **Respecting existing investments:** Communities have invested time and resources in their current data; we enhance rather than replace;
 - **Leveraging domain expertise:** Existing datasets come with community knowledge about quality, limitations, and appropriate uses;
 - **Building on established standards:** Many datasets already follow domain-specific standards that can be enhanced with FAIR principles;
- **Scalability and Sustainability**
 - **Proven data value:** Using datasets communities rely on ensures our FAIR enhancements will be maintained and used;
 - **Established workflows:** Building FAIR practices into existing workflows increases adoption likelihood;
 - **Community ownership:** Communities remain owners of their data while gaining FAIR capabilities;

- **Demonstrating FAIR Impact**
 - **Before/after comparison:** Using existing datasets allows clear demonstration of FAIR improvements;
 - **Practical benefits:** Communities can immediately see how FAIRification improves their ability to discover, access, and reuse their own data;
 - **Cross-community learning:** Showing how FAIR principles work across different CCA domains and data types.

2.2. Case Study 1: Arctic radioisotopes

Spreading radioactive isotopes in the Arctic under different climate scenarios.

Case Study 1 focuses on understanding the climate change impact on the spread of radioactive isotopes in the Arctic under different climate scenarios. The main objectives are to analyze climate predictions generated by the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) under predefined scenarios and assess the resulting changes in radionuclide distribution. This will help determine the exposure levels to the local population and wildlife, which is crucial for public and environmental safety.

Community: Arctic climate researchers, radiological safety experts, indigenous communities.

FIP Status: Development phase - stakeholder consultation ongoing.

Primary Data Sources: Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) climate predictions (data sample is available on a dedicated MinIO bucket maintained for the project (**MinIO server:** <https://server-data.fair2adapt.sigma2.no> and **bucket name:** CS1) , radioactive discharge data from RADD¹, EURDEP², and REMdb databases³.

Primary Data Formats: Climate model outputs (NetCDF⁴, Zarr⁵), Observational climate data (NetCDF), Radioactive contamination data (CSV⁶ and TSV).

Expected size of data: about 50 TB.

Data Management and FAIRification Approach:

The climate prediction data generated by the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) is produced on Norwegian High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems and stored in the **Norwegian Research Data Storage (NIRD Storage)** for the duration of the project. However, this data is not initially designed to be FAIR and will undergo the **FAIR2Adapt FAIRification framework** to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles. This process will involve adding the necessary metadata, improving accessibility, and converting the data into standardized, reusable formats.

To facilitate data sharing and collaboration during the project, samples of the NorESM data will be made publicly available via:

¹ <https://europa.eu/radd/>

² <https://remon.jrc.ec.europa.eu/About/Rad-Data-Exchange>

³ <https://remon.jrc.ec.europa.eu/About/Environmental-Monitoring/REMdb>

⁴ http://edamontology.org/format_3650

⁵ http://edamontology.org/format_3915

⁶ http://edamontology.org/format_3915 and http://edamontology.org/format_3475

- **EGI DataHub**
- **Pangeo@EOSC Object Storage**
- **Norwegian Infrastructure Object Storage (via minIO server:**
<https://server-data.fair2adapt.sigma2.no>)

These platforms will ensure that project partners have continuous access to the data throughout the project, contributing to the FAIRification efforts. Once the data is fully **FAIRified**, it will be deposited in the **Norwegian Research Data Archive** for long-term preservation, and the corresponding **Research Objects (FDOs)** will be made available in **ROHub** to support accessibility and reuse.

Long-Term Data Preservation:

The long-term preservation of the data will be ensured through trusted repositories such as the **NIRD Archive**. This platform will guarantee that the data remains accessible and compliant with **FAIR** principles after the project concludes.

Stakeholders and Data Implications:

Key stakeholders such as the **Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)**, **Tromsø Municipality**, and **Troms & Finnmark County** will rely on the data outputs from this case study to inform climate change adaptation strategies. For these stakeholders, the FAIRification and accessibility of the NorESM data imply that:

- The data will be structured in a way that aligns with international standards for interoperability.
- Metadata will be provided to ensure that the data is understandable and usable for both technical and non-technical users.
- The data will be openly accessible and reusable for future climate assessments, supporting informed decision-making for public health and environmental safety.

Data Repositories Involved:

- **Norwegian Research Data Archive (NIRD)**⁷: For long-term storage of the NorESM climate prediction data.
- **RADD (Radioactive Discharges Database)**, **EURDEP (European Radiological Data Exchange Platform)**, and **REMdb (EU Database of Radioactivity Monitoring Results)**: For domain-specific radioactive data and related environmental datasets.

Community-Endorsed FAIR Resources (Preliminary):

⁷ <https://archive.sigma2.no/>

- **Metadata Standards:** CF-Conventions⁸ for climate data, INSPIRE⁹ for geographic data
- **Vocabularies:** NERC vocabulary¹⁰ for oceanographic terms, Arctic-specific terminologies;
- **Repositories:** Norwegian Research Data Archive (NIRD), Arctic monitoring databases
- **Tools:** Arctic data visualization platforms, indigenous knowledge integration protocols

2.3. Case Study 2: Biscayan RiOMar

Coastal Water Quality Anticipation to manage coastal zone ecosystem responses for biodiversity conservation.

Case Study 2 focuses on assessing the impact of climate change on coastal water quality and marine ecosystems in France, with the aim of supporting local stakeholders, such as oyster farmers, in adapting to emerging climate-related challenges.

Community: Marine researchers, coastal managers, aquaculture industry.

FIP Status: Standards identification phase.

Primary Data Sources: RiOMar model outputs from IFREMER's Datarmor system (<https://data-fair2adapt.ifremer.fr/riomar/>), marine observation data from JERICO-RI¹¹, SOMLIT¹², MOOSE¹³, PHYTOBS networks¹⁴.

Primary Data Formats: RiOMar model outputs (NetCDF, Zarr), observations (netCDF, text/reports), Climate data (NetCDF), ODV¹⁵ (Ocean Data View files contain a header with SeaDataNet compliant metadata, followed by a line with column headers and units, and a series of data lines).

Expected size of data: about 250 TB.

⁸ <https://cfconventions.org/>

⁹ https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/metadata-technical-guidelines_en

¹⁰ <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>

¹¹ <https://www.jerico-ri.eu/>

¹² <https://www.somlit.fr/en/>

¹³ <https://campagnes.flotteoceanographique.fr/series/233/>

¹⁴ <https://www.phytobs.fr/en>

¹⁵ <https://odv.awi.de/>

Data Management and FAIRification Approach:

The **RiOMar model** generates high-resolution data related to coastal water quality and marine ecosystems, particularly focusing on river-dominated ocean margins. These datasets are produced on the **Datarmor supercomputer** at **Ifremer** and shared via **Datamor** (the data portal for Ifremer's computational and data storage center) using **HTTPS** for access during the project (<https://data-fair2adapt.ifremer.fr/riomar/>). These data are crucial for understanding the vulnerability of coastal ecosystems and supporting climate change adaptation (CCA) strategies, but they currently face significant barriers to accessibility due to their large size and complexity.

To make the RiOMar data more accessible and reusable, the data will be transformed into **Analysis Ready Cloud Optimised (ARCO)** data formats, which will improve their usability for stakeholders. The transformation will include the addition of standardized metadata to ensure the data complies with **FAIR** principles—making it **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable**, and **Reusable**. This process will be guided by the **FAIR2Adapt framework** for FAIRification.

Once the data has been **FAIRified**, it will be shared via platforms such as:

- **Pangeo@EOSC** for large-scale data analysis and integration.
- **JERICO-RI, CoastPredict¹⁶**, and other related EU repositories for coastal and marine ecosystem data.

Additionally, the **French Biodiversity Office¹⁷ (OFB)**, **Regional River Agencies¹⁸**, and professional users, including aquaculture farmers, will be able to easily access the **FAIRified** datasets through **FDOs (Fair Digital Objects)**, enabling them to develop scientifically-based CCA strategies and vulnerability maps. Tools will be developed to assist stakeholders in interpreting the data and creating these maps, ensuring that the data can be used to identify risks and vulnerabilities related to coastal zone ecosystems.

Long-Term Data Preservation:

For long-term preservation, the FAIR2Adapt project will ensure that the **RiOMar data** is archived in trusted repositories such as the **Norwegian Research Data Archive (NIRD)** or **PSNC (via ROHub)**. These repositories support **FAIR** compliance and long-term availability. Additionally, access will be provided through **FDOs** in platforms like **ROHub**, enabling ongoing use and accessibility for stakeholders and the scientific community.

¹⁶ <https://www.coastpredict.org/>

¹⁷ <https://www.ofb.gouv.fr/en>

¹⁸ <https://www.lesagencesdeleau.fr/>

Stakeholders and Data Implications:

The key stakeholders involved in the coastal water quality case study include the **French Biodiversity Office (OFB)**, **Regional River Agencies**, and **professional users of the coastal zone**, such as **aquaculture farming structures**. By applying the **FAIRification** process to the RiOMar data, the project will ensure that:

- Data is **accessible** and **interoperable** across different platforms and tools.
- **Risk and vulnerability maps** can be easily created to support decision-making processes related to **climate change adaptation**.
- Data is made available in **French**, addressing language barriers for local stakeholders.
- The long-term preservation of the data ensures its continued use by stakeholders involved in biodiversity conservation, aquaculture management, and regional policy planning.

Data Repositories Involved:

- **Datamor**: The data storage system at Ifremer, which will host the initial RiOMar data.
- **Norwegian Research Data Archive (NIRD)** or **PSNC**: For long-term archiving and preservation of the data once it has been FAIRified.
- **JERICO-RI**, **SOMLIT**, **MOOSE**, **PHYTOBS**, and **CoastPredict**: These EU and regional platforms will also host and facilitate access to specific marine and coastal data relevant to the case study.

Community-Endorsed FAIR Resources (Preliminary):

- **Metadata Standards**: SeaDataNet standards¹⁹, INSPIRE marine themes²⁰
- **Vocabularies**: Marine vocabulary from BODC²¹, French marine terminologies
- **Repositories**: French marine data infrastructure, JERICO-RI repositories, PANGAEA²²
- **Tools**: ARCO data transformation tools, coastal risk assessment tools and dashboards (to be developed)

2.4. Case Study 3: City of Hamburg

Climate-induced stressors and their effects on urban societies.

¹⁹ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards>

²⁰ https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/oceanographic-geographical-features_en

²¹ <https://www.bodc.ac.uk/>

²² <https://www.pangaea.de/>

Case Study 3 focuses on assessing urban climate risks in Hamburg, Germany, by integrating climate hazard data with socio-economic vulnerability data to inform sustainable, cross-sectoral climate change adaptation strategies.

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** will define the processes for:

- **Data collection:** How climate and socio-economic data are collected, managed, and curated by Hamburg City authorities.
- **FAIRification:** Steps to ensure data complies with **FAIR** principles.
- **Data sharing:** The platforms and tools through which the **FAIRified** data will be shared with stakeholders, including **Geoportal Hamburg** and **Copernicus**.
- **Data integration:** The creation of **semantic crosswalks** to integrate **climate hazard data** with **socio-economic vulnerability** data, enabling a comprehensive risk analysis.
- **Long-term preservation:** Plans for archiving the data in **the Hamburg data and modelling platforms as well as in trusted repositories (Zenodo)** and linking it with RoHub for sustained access.

Community: Urban planners, climate services, municipal authorities.

FIP Status: Municipal data inventory complete, standards selection in progress.

Primary Data Sources: Hamburg's Geoportal (572 datasets)²³, German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) data²⁴, Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S) data²⁵.

Hamburg's Climate Data Assets: The city maintains comprehensive climate-related datasets including:

- Flood risk maps and inundation scenarios;
- Urban heat island mapping and temperature projections;
- Heavy precipitation risk assessments
- Storm surge and wind exposure data
- Infrastructure vulnerability to climate stressors
- Population exposure and demographic vulnerability data
- Green infrastructure and adaptation measure effectiveness data

Primary Data Formats: Socio-economic datasets (CSV, Excel²⁶, Shapefile), Geographic data (GeoTIFF, Shapefile, GeoJSON), ArcGIS.

²³ <https://www.en.urbandataplatform.hamburg/>

²⁴ <https://www.dkrz.de/en/dkrz-partner-for-climate-research>

²⁵ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>

²⁶ http://edamontology.org/format_3620

Expected size of data: about 0.5 TB.

Data Management and FAIRification Approach:

The city of **Hamburg** faces multiple climate-related risks, and there is an urgent need for a **systematic, sustainable, and cross-sectoral approach** to climate change adaptation (CCA). To support this, the city has collected **granulated data** on exposure and vulnerability across urban sectors, infrastructure, and populations, as well as data on climate-induced stressors. This data, managed by different city authorities under the **Hamburg City Senate**, is stored in the **Hamburg Urban Data Portal**, but it is not always publicly available or updated, making it difficult to effectively use in adaptation planning.

Through the **FAIR2Adapt project**, the available data (including models/software) will undergo a **FAIRification** process to improve their **Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR)**.

Once **FAIRified**, the data (datasets, model, software, workflows) will be made available through the Urban Data Platform and the Urban Modelling Platform of **Hamburg** with corresponding FDOs available in RoHub.

Long-Term Data Preservation:

For long-term access and preservation, the **FAIRified** data will be deposited in **trusted** repositories such as the Hamburg Urban data and modeling platforms, as well as on Zenodo (software). This will ensure that the data remains **accessible** and **interoperable** for future adaptation planning.

Stakeholders and Data Implications:

The **Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg Senate Chancellery** is the lead authority for the climate adaptation work in Hamburg. The **FAIRification** process will help the city improve its **data sharing** capabilities and provide **updated, high-resolution data** for decision-making. By integrating **climate hazard data** with **socio-economic vulnerability data**, the city will be able to better understand the **future climate risks** it faces, identify **barriers to adaptation**, and develop **tailored adaptation scenarios** (e.g., **RCPs** and **SSPs**). This will support the creation of scientifically-based **climate risk assessments** and ensure that **climate adaptation strategies** are based on comprehensive, **high-quality data**.

Data Repositories Involved:

- **Hamburg Urban Data and Modelling Platforms:** The primary data and modelling portals for the city, which will house the **FAIRified** datasets and models, respectively.
- **German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ):** Provides access to climate data and computational resources for the city's climate adaptation efforts.

- **Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S) Data Store:** Global data resources that will complement Hamburg’s local data to offer a broader context for adaptation planning.
- **Climate Risk Dashboard:** A tool that will be developed within WP4 and integrated with the FAIRified data to allow stakeholders to access up-to-date climate risk information.

Community-Endorsed FAIR Resources (Preliminary):

- **Metadata Standards:** INSPIRE for urban/environmental data, ISO 19115²⁷ for geographic information, OAF²⁸ (OGC API Feature), STA²⁹ (Sensor Thing API), WMS³⁰ (Web Mapping Service), WFS³¹ (Web Feature Service);
- **Vocabularies:** GEMET³² environmental thesaurus, German municipal data standards;
- **Repositories:** Hamburg Urban Data Platform, German climate data center (DKRZ);
- **Tools:** Urban climate modeling platforms, vulnerability assessment tools (developed by researchers from the University of Hamburg).

2.5. Case Study 4: Designing a FAIR national adaptation hub

Developing and testing a FAIR-by-design national adaptation hub.

Case Study 4 focuses on developing and testing a **FAIR-by-design national adaptation hub** that serves as a blueprint for other Member States. This case study addresses the challenge that countries and regions face in building resilience to climate change impacts, particularly in response to the EU's call for smarter, faster, and more systemic adaptation as outlined in the 2021 EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. The primary data management goals are:

- **Aggregating distributed knowledge:** Finding, extracting, curating and making available climate and non-climate knowledge from fragmented sources
- **Creating interlinked FDOs:** Establishing connections between Data FDOs, Executable FDOs, and Knowledge-related FDOs
- **Supporting decision-making:** Enabling stakeholders to access tailored, locally-relevant information for adaptation strategies

²⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html>

²⁸ <https://ogcapi.ogc.org/features/>

²⁹ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/sensorthings/>

³⁰ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/wms/>

³¹ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/wfs/>

³² <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/about/>

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** will define the processes for:

- **Data Collection:**
 - **Systematic harvesting** from Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT, MIP4Adapt, C3S, and Portuguese national portals using automated APIs and web scraping.
 - **Stakeholder-driven content identification** through workshops with 48 Mission signatories to prioritize relevant datasets and knowledge resources.
 - **Expert curation** by Portuguese researchers and policy makers to validate collected content and fill identified gaps.
 - **Multilingual content acquisition** ensuring both Portuguese and English materials are captured with priority on locally-relevant sources.
- **FAIRification:**
 - **Metadata standardization** using European adaptation schemas combined with Portuguese national data standards and multilingual vocabularies.
 - **Content structuring** into Data, Executable, and Knowledge FDOs using appropriate RO-Crate profiles for each category.
 - **Semantic enhancement** using I-ADOPT framework and custom Portuguese climate adaptation terminologies.
 - **Quality assessment** through FAIR evaluation metrics adapted for policy-relevant content and stakeholder usability.
- **Data Sharing:**
 - **National hub portal** providing public access with Portuguese-language interface and stakeholder-specific views.
 - **API development** enabling programmatic access to FDOs for integration with existing Portuguese institutional systems.
 - **European platform integration** maintaining connections with Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT, and other EU-level adaptation platforms.
 - **Tiered access model** with open access for aggregated data and controlled access for sensitive policy documents.
- **Data Integration:**
 - **Cross-platform harmonization** creating semantic mappings between different source vocabularies and metadata schemas.
 - **FDO interlinking** establishing machine-readable connections between related Data, Executable, and Knowledge FDOs.
 - **Stakeholder workflow alignment** organizing content according to the 6-step RAST methodology used by EU Mission.
 - **Multi-scale integration** connecting national-level policies with regional implementation examples and local case studies.
- **Long-term Preservation:**

- **National repository integration** depositing core datasets in Portuguese institutional repositories with long-term preservation commitments.
- **European backup systems** maintaining copies in EOSC-federated repositories (Zenodo, ROHub) for redundancy and accessibility.
- **Migration strategies** planning for technology evolution including format updates, platform transitions, and metadata schema evolution.
- **Community sustainability** transferring maintenance responsibilities to Portuguese national institutions with documented procedures and training.

Community: National adaptation coordinators, policy makers, regional authorities, knowledge producers, knowledge brokers, and all Portuguese Mission signatories (48 as of January 2024).

FIP Status: Requirements gathering phase.

Primary Challenge: The proliferation of national and regional adaptation portals, platforms, and initiatives has led to confusion among users about good practice and relevant, credible information. This case study aims to create a centralized, FAIR-compliant solution that aggregates distributed knowledge while avoiding duplication of effort.

Primary Data Sources:

National Policy and Strategy Documents:

- National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change 2020 (Estratégia Nacional de Adaptação às Alterações Climáticas 2020³³)
- Metropolitan Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change (Plano Metropolitano de Adaptação às Alterações Climáticas³⁴)
- Action Programme for Adaptation to Climate Change (Programa de Ação para a Adaptação às Alterações Climáticas - P-3AC³⁵)
- Climate Base Law 2021 (Lei de Bases do Clima 2021³⁶)
- National Roadmap for Adaptation 2100 (Roteiro Nacional para a Adaptação 2100³⁷)

National Data Platforms:

³³

<https://www.planapp.gov.pt/instrumento-planeame/estrategia-nacional-adaptacao-alteracoes-climaticas/>

³⁴ <https://www.aml.pt/iniciativas/plano-adaptacao-alteracoes-climaticas/>

³⁵ <https://apambiente.pt/clima/programa-de-acao-para-adaptacao-alteracoes-climaticas-p-3ac>

³⁶ <https://files.dre.pt/1s/2021/12/25300/0000500032.pdf>

³⁷ <https://apambiente.pt/clima/roteiro-nacional-para-adaptacao-2100>

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

- Portal do clima (<http://portaldoclima.pt/pt/>) - Portuguese Climate Portal
- INE (<https://www.ine.pt/>) - Portuguese National Statistics Institute
- adapt.local (<https://www.adapt-local.pt/>) - Local adaptation platform
- IPMA - Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere³⁸

Research Infrastructure and Projects:

- IMPECAF project: Impacts of extreme climatic events on agricultural and forestry systems (<http://impecaf.rd.ciencias.ulisboa.pt/>)
- Climate Risk Dashboard (<https://climate-risk-dashboard.iiasa.ac.at/>)
- Strategic framework on Climate Policy (QEPiC framework) (<https://www.ecolex.org/details/legislation/strategic-framework-on-climate-policy-le-x-faoc148610/>)
- [Population census 2021 data](#)

Comprehensive Scientific Literature Base (150+ publications currently being compiled for this case study):

- Climate projections and extremes studies for Portugal
- Regional climate modeling and impacts assessment
- Sectoral adaptation research (agriculture, forestry, coastal, urban)
- Heat wave, drought, and wildfire impact studies
- Ecosystem and biodiversity response studies
- Socio-economic impact assessments
- Urban climate and thermal comfort research

Global adaptation platforms: Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT, MIP4Adapt

EU thematic services: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), DestinE Climate Adaptation³⁹ and Extreme Events Digital Twin⁴⁰ available from the DestinE platform⁴¹

International scenario databases: PROVIDE Climate Risk Dashboard⁴², IIASA SSP Scenario Explorer⁴³

Stakeholder-driven content: Input from 48 Portuguese Mission signatories

Primary Data Formats: Socio-economic datasets (CSV, Excel, Shapefile), Policy documents and reports (PDF, DOC), Geographic data (GeoTIFF, Shapefile, GeoJSON).

³⁸ <https://www.ipma.pt/en/oipma/quem/ipma/>

³⁹ https://hda.central.data.destination-earth.eu/ui/dataset/EO.ECMWF.DAT.DT_CLIMATE_ADAPTATION

⁴⁰ <https://destine.ecmwf.int/weather-induced-extremes-digital-twin/#Access-the-Extremes-DT-data>

⁴¹ <https://platform.destine.eu/>

⁴² <https://climate-risk-dashboard.iiasa.ac.at/>

⁴³ <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ssp/#/login?redirect=%2Fworkspaces>

Expected size of data: Approximately 1 TB.

Data Management and FAIRification Approach:

The case study employs a comprehensive multi-source aggregation strategy from fragmented European and national platforms. Based on the systematic inventory of Portuguese climate adaptation resources, the following data categories have been identified:

Data Categorization and Volume:

- **Policy documents:** 8 national strategies, plans, and legal frameworks
- **Web platforms:** national data portals and research platforms
- **Research reports:** RNA2100 reports covering climate projections, impacts, and adaptation strategies
- **Scientific publications:** 150+ peer-reviewed articles covering:
 - Climate modeling and projections (25+ papers)
 - Heat stress and temperature impacts (30+ papers)
 - Agricultural and forestry adaptation (25+ papers)
 - Urban climate and thermal comfort (20+ papers)
 - Coastal and marine impacts (15+ papers)
 - Ecosystem and biodiversity responses (20+ papers)
 - Socio-economic and health impacts (15+ papers)
- **Datasets:** Climate observations, census data, sectoral indicators
- **Tools and models:** Climate risk assessment tools, adaptation planning frameworks

Data Collection Process:

- **Systematic harvesting:** Automated collection from Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT, MIP4Adapt, C3S, and Portuguese national portals using APIs and web scraping
- **Stakeholder-driven identification:** Workshops with Portuguese Mission signatories to prioritize relevant datasets and knowledge resources
- **Expert curation:** Portuguese researchers and policy makers validate collected content and identify gaps
- **Multilingual content acquisition:** Capturing both Portuguese and English materials with priority on locally-relevant sources

FAIRification Process:

- **Metadata standardization:** Using European adaptation schemas combined with Portuguese national data standards and multilingual vocabularies

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

- **Content structuring:** Organizing content into appropriate FDO categories using RO-Crate profiles
- **Semantic enhancement:** Applying I-ADOPT framework and custom Portuguese climate adaptation terminologies
- **Quality assessment:** Using FAIR evaluation metrics adapted for policy-relevant content and stakeholder usability

Data Sharing Strategy:

- **National hub portal:** Public access with Portuguese-language interface and stakeholder-specific views
- **API development:** Programmatic access to FDOs for integration with existing Portuguese institutional systems
- **European platform integration:** Maintaining connections with Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT, and other EU-level adaptation platforms
- **Tiered access model:** Open access for aggregated data and controlled access for sensitive policy documents

Data Integration Approach:

- **Cross-platform harmonization:** Creating semantic mappings between different source vocabularies and metadata schemas
- **FDO interlinking:** Establishing machine-readable connections between related Data, Executable, and Knowledge FDOs
- **Stakeholder workflow alignment:** Organizing content according to the 6-step RAST (Regional Adaptation Support Tool) methodology used by EU Mission
- **Multi-scale integration:** Connecting national-level policies with regional implementation examples and local case studies

Long-Term Data Preservation:

The preservation strategy is designed to avoid duplication while ensuring sustainability:

- **Versioned FDOs:** Digital Objects designed to evolve beyond project lifetime with automatic or semi-automatic updates when new data becomes available
- **Reference-based approach:** FDOs reference original data sources rather than containing duplicate data
- **National repository integration:** Core datasets deposited in Portuguese institutional repositories with long-term preservation commitments
- **European backup systems:** Copies maintained in EOSC-federated repositories (Zenodo, ROHub) for redundancy and accessibility

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- **Migration strategies:** Planning for technology evolution including format updates, platform transitions, and metadata schema evolution
- **Community sustainability:** Transferring maintenance responsibilities to Portuguese national institutions with documented procedures and training

Stakeholders and Data Implications:

Four main stakeholder categories:

1. **National agencies:** Environmental agencies, government departments
2. **Knowledge producers:** Research centers, state laboratories, insurers
3. **Knowledge brokers:** Academia, consultancies, climate service providers
4. **Mission signatories:** All 48 Portuguese Mission signatories

Key benefits for stakeholders:

- **Centralized access:** Single portal for fragmented adaptation information
- **Language accessibility:** Portuguese-language interface with multilingual metadata
- **Decision-support tools:** Tailored, locally-relevant information for adaptation strategies
- **FAIR capacity building:** Training and resources for implementing FAIR practices
- **National impact:** Bridging research-policy gap through evidence-based information

Data Repositories Involved:

- **National sources:** Portuguese Climate Portal, Statistics Portugal
- **European platforms:** Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT, MIP4Adapt, DestinE, C3S
- **International databases:** PROVIDE Climate Risk Dashboard, IIASA scenario explorers
- **Data preservation:** Zenodo, ROHub for European accessibility
- **Institutional archives:** Portuguese university and government repositories

Community-Endorsed FAIR Resources (Preliminary):

- **Metadata Standards:** European adaptation metadata schemas, Portuguese national data standards
- **Vocabularies:** Climate adaptation terminologies in Portuguese, EU policy vocabularies
- **Repositories:** National climate data repositories, European adaptation platforms
- **Tools:** National adaptation hub infrastructure, multi-lingual content management systems

2.6. Case Study 5: Enriching weADAPT and the connectivity hub global

Connecting and visualising the CCA knowledge landscape through the Connectivity Hub and weADAPT.

Case Study 5 focuses on enhancing global climate adaptation knowledge platforms to break down silos and improve searchability of fragmented adaptation information across multiple languages and cultural contexts. The case study addresses the challenge that users cannot quickly find relevant information due to fragmented, unstructured, and siloed knowledge, by using AI to automatically construct taxonomies and knowledge graphs that visualize content relationships and improve discoverability. This work involves harvesting, curating, and FAIRifying climate and non-climate information from popular knowledge portals, platforms, and publications to support the development and implementation of adaptation planning at global, national, regional, and local scales.

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** will define the processes for:

- **Data Collection:**

- **Automated content harvesting** from weADAPT⁴⁴, Connectivity Hub⁴⁵, and partner knowledge platforms using web scraping APIs and content management system integration.
- **Global case study aggregation** collecting adaptation practices, policy documents, and implementation examples from diverse geographic and cultural contexts.
- **Multi-language content acquisition** capturing knowledge resources in multiple languages to ensure global representation and accessibility.
- **Community-contributed content** through platform user submissions, expert nominations, and stakeholder-driven content identification workshops.

- **FAIRification:**

- **AI-driven metadata extraction** using natural language processing to automatically generate structured metadata from unstructured text documents and case studies.
- **Automated taxonomy construction** employing machine learning to identify relationships between concepts and create hierarchical knowledge organization structures.

⁴⁴ <https://weadapt.org/>

⁴⁵ <https://connectivity-hub.placard-network.eu/>

- **Cross-cultural terminology mapping** developing semantic bridges between adaptation concepts expressed in different languages and cultural contexts.
- **Knowledge graph generation** creating machine-readable representations of relationships between adaptation concepts, locations, stakeholders, and practices.
- **Data Sharing:**
 - **Enhanced platform interfaces** providing improved search and discovery capabilities on weADAPT and Connectivity Hub with natural language querying.
 - **API development** enabling programmatic access to FAIRified knowledge graphs and taxonomies for integration with other adaptation platforms.
 - **Multilingual accessibility** ensuring content and search capabilities are available in multiple languages to serve global user communities.
 - **Visualization dashboards** offering interactive knowledge maps and relationship browsers to help users navigate complex adaptation landscapes.
- **Data Integration:**
 - **Cross-platform knowledge linking** creating semantic connections between content on weADAPT, Connectivity Hub, and external adaptation knowledge sources.
 - **Taxonomic harmonization** aligning different classification schemes used across global adaptation platforms and organizations.
 - **Cultural context preservation** maintaining original terminology and concepts while creating mappings for cross-cultural knowledge exchange.
 - **Temporal integration** connecting historical adaptation experiences with current practices and future planning scenarios.
- **Long-term Preservation:**
 - **Platform-native preservation** ensuring long-term accessibility through weADAPT and Connectivity Hub infrastructure with community governance models.
 - **Knowledge graph archiving** depositing structured taxonomies and relationship data in persistent repositories like Zenodo and FAIR knowledge bases.
 - **Community sustainability** establishing global user communities and institutional partnerships to maintain and update knowledge resources over time.
 - **Format migration strategies** planning for evolution of knowledge representation standards and platform technologies to ensure continued accessibility.

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

Community: Global adaptation practitioners, knowledge brokers, researchers.

FIP Status: Platform analysis ongoing.

Primary Data Sources: Content from weADAPT platform and Connectivity Hub knowledge repositories, global adaptation case studies and practices.

Primary Data Formats: Policy documents and reports (PDF, DOC).

Expected size of data: about 5 TB.

Data Management and FAIRification Approach:

The global knowledge platforms will be enhanced through AI-driven analysis of existing content to automatically construct taxonomies, knowledge graphs, and cross-cultural terminology mappings that improve searchability and discoverability of adaptation information. The FAIRification process involves automated metadata extraction from multilingual text documents, machine learning-based relationship identification between adaptation concepts, and creation of interactive visualization tools that help users navigate complex knowledge landscapes across different languages, cultures, and geographic contexts.

Long-Term Data Preservation:

Knowledge resources will be preserved through the existing governance models of weADAPT and Connectivity Hub platforms, complemented by archiving of structured knowledge graphs and taxonomies in persistent repositories like Zenodo and specialized knowledge bases. The sustainability strategy relies on global community engagement, institutional partnerships with major adaptation organizations, and format migration planning to ensure knowledge remains accessible as technologies and standards evolve over time.

Stakeholders and Data Implications:

Key stakeholders include global adaptation practitioners, knowledge producers and brokers, decision-makers and policy-makers, governmental agencies, and citizens worldwide who need access to adaptation information. For these stakeholders, the FAIRification process means dramatically improved ability to find relevant adaptation knowledge across language and cultural barriers, access to AI-generated insights about relationships between different adaptation approaches, and enhanced collaboration opportunities through better understanding of who is working on similar challenges globally.

Data Repositories Involved:

- **weADAPT platform** - Primary global adaptation knowledge repository with case studies, guidance materials, and community-contributed content
- **Connectivity Hub** - Knowledge visualization and relationship mapping platform for climate resilience information
- **International knowledge platforms** - Partner repositories including Climate-ADAPT, MIP4Adapt, and regional adaptation networks
- **Zenodo and persistent archives** - Long-term preservation of structured knowledge graphs, taxonomies, and AI-generated metadata
- **Multilingual knowledge bases** - Specialized repositories for cross-cultural terminology and translation resources.

Community-Endorsed FAIR Resources (Preliminary):

- **Metadata Standards:** Knowledge organization schemas, multilingual metadata standards;
- **Vocabularies:** Global adaptation taxonomies, cross-cultural climate terminologies;
- **Repositories:** weADAPT, Connectivity Hub, international knowledge platforms;
- **Tools:** AI-driven content analysis, knowledge graph visualization, taxonomy builders.

2.7. Case Study 6: FAIR Climate risk data for businesses

Improving data availability for climate risk assessments under the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities.

Case Study 6 focuses on addressing the challenge that businesses and consultants face when conducting climate risk assessments required under EU Taxonomy regulations, where data for the mandatory 28 climate hazards is scattered across multiple European, national, and local sources without harmonized tagging or structure. The case study works with two businesses across multiple EU countries to document current data sources, identify gaps, and develop FAIR approaches to make climate hazard data more accessible and compliant with EU Taxonomy requirements, ultimately creating a replicable framework for harmonized climate risk data access that supports both regulatory compliance and informed business decision-making.

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** will define the processes for:

- **Data Collection:**

- **Multi-scale hazard data aggregation** from European (Risk Data Hub⁴⁶, Copernicus⁴⁷), national (flood/drought maps, weather services), and local (urban heat maps, municipal adaptation strategies) sources across multiple EU countries.
- **Business case documentation** through direct collaboration with two companies to track their actual data usage, sources, and gaps during EU Taxonomy compliance assessments.
- **Regulatory requirement mapping** systematically cataloguing data needs for all 28 mandatory climate hazards specified in EU Taxonomy regulations.
- **Cross-jurisdictional harmonization** collecting equivalent datasets from different EU member states to enable consistent multi-country business assessments.
- **FAIRification:**
 - **EU Taxonomy-compliant metadata** development ensuring all climate hazard datasets include required regulatory information and compliance indicators.
 - **Business-oriented data structuring** organizing climate data according to business risk assessment workflows and financial sector requirements rather than scientific research needs.
 - **Harmonized hazard classification** creating consistent tagging and vocabulary systems that align scattered datasets with the 28 EU Taxonomy climate hazards.
 - **Accessibility enhancement** transforming technical climate data into business-readable formats with appropriate uncertainty quantification and spatial/temporal resolution documentation.
- **Data Sharing:**
 - **Business-focused data portals** providing streamlined access interfaces designed for risk analysts and compliance consultants rather than climate scientists.
 - **Multi-country data federation** enabling businesses with operations across EU countries to access harmonized datasets through single access points.
 - **Compliance reporting integration** developing APIs and data formats that can be directly integrated into EU Taxonomy reporting workflows and business risk management systems.
 - **Tiered access models** balancing public availability of aggregated data with commercial licensing for high-resolution, value-added datasets.
- **Data Integration:**

⁴⁶ <https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.copernicus.eu/en>

- **Cross-scale harmonization** linking European-level climate projections with national risk maps and local adaptation measures to provide comprehensive business risk context.
- **Temporal alignment** integrating historical observations, current conditions, and future projections to support the long-term risk assessments required by EU Taxonomy.
- **Business process integration** organizing data according to standard risk assessment methodologies used by financial sector and compliance consultants.
- **Regulatory framework mapping** ensuring data organization aligns with EU Taxonomy structure and other relevant financial regulations (TCFD, CSRD, etc.).
- **Long-term Preservation:**
 - **Regulatory compliance archiving** maintaining historical versions of datasets and methodologies to support audit trails and regulatory reporting requirements.
 - **Business continuity planning** ensuring data availability through multiple channels and backup systems to support ongoing compliance obligations.
 - **Version control systems** tracking changes in both source datasets and regulatory requirements to maintain compliance over time.
 - **Industry standard integration** aligning with financial sector data preservation practices and audit requirements for long-term accessibility.

Community: Business risk analysts, financial sector, compliance consultants.

FIP Status: Requirements analysis phase ongoing.

Primary Data Sources: European climate hazard datasets from Risk Data Hub, Copernicus missions, EURO-CORDEX⁴⁸, national flood/drought data, local adaptation strategies.

Primary Data Formats: Socio-economic datasets (CSV, Excel, Shapefile), Policy documents and reports (PDF, DOC), Geographic data (GeoTIFF, Shapefile, GeoJSON), Jupyter notebooks (JSON).

Expected size of data: about 1 TB.

⁴⁸ <https://www.euro-cordex.net/>

Data Management and FAIRification Approach:

The business climate risk data framework will be developed through direct collaboration with two multi-country businesses to document real-world data usage patterns and gaps in EU Taxonomy compliance assessments, then create FAIR solutions that harmonize the scattered landscape of European, national, and local climate hazard data. The FAIRification process emphasizes business-oriented metadata that includes regulatory compliance information, harmonized vocabularies aligned with the 28 mandatory EU Taxonomy climate hazards, and accessible data formats designed for risk analysts rather than climate scientists, ensuring that technical climate data can be efficiently integrated into business risk management and regulatory reporting workflows.

Long-Term Data Preservation:

Climate risk data will be preserved through integration with existing European risk databases and business climate data platforms, with emphasis on maintaining regulatory compliance audit trails and version control systems that track both dataset changes and evolving EU requirements. The sustainability strategy includes alignment with financial sector data governance standards, business continuity planning for ongoing compliance obligations, and integration with established risk management platforms used by the financial industry to ensure long-term accessibility and regulatory acceptance.

Stakeholders and Data Implications:

Key stakeholders include European businesses subject to EU Taxonomy reporting (particularly in manufacturing and water infrastructure sectors), climate risk consultants, financial institutions conducting due diligence, and regulatory bodies overseeing compliance. For these stakeholders, the FAIRification process means dramatically reduced time and cost for conducting EU Taxonomy climate risk assessments, harmonized data access across multiple EU countries for businesses with distributed operations, standardized methodologies that ensure regulatory compliance and audit readiness, and improved business decision-making through better access to relevant local-scale climate risk information.

Data Repositories Involved:

- **European Risk Data Hub and Copernicus Climate Data Store** - Primary sources for EU-wide climate hazard data and satellite-based observations
- **National meteorological and environmental agencies** - Country-specific flood maps, drought indicators, and weather extreme datasets across multiple EU member states
- **Local and regional adaptation databases** - Municipal climate risk assessments, urban heat mapping, and local adaptation strategy repositories

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

- **Business climate data platforms and financial risk databases** - Commercial and institutional repositories used by the financial sector for climate risk assessment
- **EU regulatory compliance repositories** - Official databases maintaining EU Taxonomy documentation, reporting templates, and compliance guidance.

Community-Endorsed FAIR Resources (Preliminary):

- **Metadata Standards:** EU Taxonomy-compliant metadata, financial risk data standards;
- **Vocabularies:** Business risk terminologies, EU regulatory vocabularies;
- **Repositories:** European risk databases, business climate data platforms;
- **Tools:** Risk assessment platforms, EU Taxonomy compliance tools, harmonized data access.

2.8. Transfer cases

Transfer cases are additional climate adaptation contexts and communities beyond the six primary case studies that will test and validate the scalability of the FAIR2Adapt FAIRification framework. These cases represent different geographic regions, climate challenges, or stakeholder groups not covered by the original case studies, allowing us to demonstrate that our FAIR data management approaches can be adapted and applied across diverse European climate adaptation contexts. As transfer cases will be defined and developed later in the project, detailed information on the datasets involved is not yet available. However, FAIR2Adapt will ensure that data management for these cases follows the same rigorous standards as for the main case studies. Specifically, the FAIRification framework developed in WP3 will guide the development of tailored DMPs for each transfer case. This includes identifying, documenting, and managing data according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and, where applicable, CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles. Once defined, each transfer case will be assessed for its data needs, and appropriate FAIR-enabling services and repositories will be selected accordingly. Updated information and evolving DMPs for the transfer cases will be integrated into the overall project DMP and made publicly accessible via ROHub.

Primary Data Formats: Socio-economic datasets (CSV, Excel, Shapefile), Policy documents and reports (PDF, DOC), Geographic data (GeoTIFF, Shapefile, GeoJSON), Jupyter notebooks (JSON), Dashboard Applications (HTML Javascript).

Expected size of data: about 4 TB.

2.9. Communication and Training Data

FAIR2Adapt will also generate data through various communication and capacity building activities:

- **Webinar recordings and presentations** documenting FAIR training sessions and community workshops;
- **Training materials and documentation** including tutorials, best practice guides, and community feedback;
- **Workshop outputs** capturing stakeholder requirements, FIP development sessions, and validation results;
- **Community engagement records** documenting lessons learned and adoption patterns

Expected size: ~0.1 TB

Primary formats: Video recordings (MP4), presentation slides (PDF), workshop notes (text/documents).

Repository: Project website, EOSC training platforms, YouTube for videos.

2.10. Data Utility Beyond FAIR2Adapt

The datasets generated and FAIRified through FAIR2Adapt will serve multiple user communities beyond the immediate project scope:

Scientific Community

- **Climate researchers:** Enhanced climate model outputs with improved metadata for comparative studies;
- **Adaptation scientists:** Standardized datasets enabling cross-regional adaptation research;
- **Social scientists:** Linked socio-economic and climate data for vulnerability assessments;
- **Computer scientists:** FAIR Digital Objects as examples for other domain applications.

Policy and Governance

- **EU Mission on Adaptation:** Standardized data supporting the 150+ regions target
- **National adaptation offices:** Templates and methodologies for national adaptation hubs
- **Regional authorities:** Local-scale data and indicators for adaptation planning
- **Municipal planners:** Urban climate risk data and vulnerability assessments

Private Sector

- **Financial institutions:** EU Taxonomy-compliant climate risk datasets
- **Insurance companies:** Standardized climate hazard data for risk modeling
- **Consulting firms:** FAIR datasets reducing data acquisition costs
- **Technology companies:** Interoperable data formats for service development

International Organizations:

- **IPCC assessments:** Standardized regional adaptation data
- **UN frameworks:** Climate adaptation indicators and methodologies
- **Development agencies:** Replicable approaches for global adaptation support

2.11. Comprehensive Data Overview

Summary Statistics

- Total Expected Data Volume: ~310 TB across all case studies and transfer cases
- Number of Case Studies: 6 primary + multiple transfer cases
- Geographic Coverage: Arctic, Atlantic coast (France), Central Europe (Germany), Iberian Peninsula (Portugal), Global platforms
- Temporal Coverage: Historical observations to multi-decadal projections
- Data Access Levels: Mixed (Open access, Restricted access, Controlled access)

Data Categories by Domain

Climate and Ocean Modeling Data (300+ TB)

- Arctic climate projections (NorESM): 50 TB
- Coastal ocean dynamics (CROCO/RiOMar): 250 TB

D1.2 – Data Management Plan

- Urban climate scenarios (Hamburg): 0.5 TB

Policy and Knowledge Data (6+ TB)

- National adaptation platforms: 1 TB
- Global knowledge repositories: 5 TB
- Business compliance data: 1 TB

Transfer Case Data (4 TB)

- Multiple domains, formats, and access levels to be determined during project implementation

Primary Model Platforms and Data Sources

Case Study 1 - Arctic Radioisotopes (50 TB)

- Model Platform: Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM)
- Primary Repositories: NIRD Archive, EURDEP, REMdb
- Data Types: Climate projections, radiological monitoring data
- Access Level: Open access with some restricted monitoring data
- Stakeholders: Arctic communities, radiological safety experts, AMAP

Case Study 2 - Biscayan RiOMar (250 TB)

- Model Platform: CROCO (Coastal and Regional Ocean COmmunity model, modified)
- Primary Repositories: Datarmor, Pangeo@EOSC, JERICO-RI, ILICO
- Data Types: High-resolution coastal ocean dynamics, biogeochemistry, marine observations
- Access Level: Open access
- Stakeholders: Marine researchers, aquaculture industry, coastal managers

Case Study 3 - Hamburg City (0.5 TB)

- Data Platform: Hamburg's Urban Data Portal (Geoportal)
- Primary Repositories: Hamburg Urban Data/Modelling Platforms, DKRZ, Copernicus C3S
- Data Types: Municipal datasets (572), flooding data, socio-economic indicators, infrastructure data
- Access Level: Mixed (public and restricted municipal data)
- Stakeholders: Urban planners, municipal authorities, climate services

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

Case Study 4 - National Hub Portugal (1 TB)

- Data Sources: Multiple European and national adaptation platforms
- Primary Repositories: Climate-ADAPT, weADAPT, MIP4Adapt, Portuguese national portals, Zenodo
- Data Types: Policy documents, climate projections, socio-economic data, case studies
- Access Level: Primarily open access
- Stakeholders: National agencies, regional authorities, 48 Mission signatories

Case Study 5 - Global Knowledge Platforms (5 TB)

- Data Platforms: weADAPT, Connectivity Hub
- Primary Repositories: Platform-native storage, Zenodo for preservation
- Data Types: Global adaptation practices, policy documents, case studies
- Access Level: Open access
- Stakeholders: Global adaptation practitioners, knowledge brokers, researchers

Case Study 6 - Business Climate Risk (1 TB)

- Data Sources: European Risk Data Hub, Copernicus, national hazard databases
- Primary Repositories: Business climate platforms, Risk Data Hub, national repositories
- Data Types: Climate hazard maps, regulatory compliance data, risk assessments
- Access Level: Mixed (public hazard data, restricted business data)
- Stakeholders: Financial sector, compliance consultants, European businesses

Repository Distribution

- EOSC-federated repositories: ROHub, Zenodo, EGI DataHub, Pangeo@EOSC
- National research infrastructures: NIRD Archive (Norway), DKRZ (Germany)
- Domain-specific platforms: JERICO-RI, ILICO, weADAPT, Connectivity Hub
- Municipal/regional platforms: Hamburg Urban Portal, Portuguese national portals
- Regulatory/business platforms: Risk Data Hub, EU Taxonomy compliance systems

Data Format Standards

- Climate data: NetCDF-4 with CF conventions, Zarr for cloud optimization
- Geographic data: GeoTIFF, Shapefile, GeoJSON-LD
- Research objects: RO-Crate profiles for different data types
- Knowledge content: PDF, HTML, JSON-LD for structured content
- Workflows and software: Jupyter notebooks, executable containers

3. Other Research Outputs

FAIR2Adapt will generate and manage a wide range of research outputs beyond traditional datasets, all of which will be managed according to FAIR principles and made available for community reuse and adaptation. These outputs include software, workflows and AI models.

Software

In the context of the FAIR2ADAPT FAIRification Framework, we will set up the following services:

- FAIR assessment service adapted and customized for climate change adaptation communities
- Automated I-ADOPT service for aligning dataset variables across different data sources
- FAIRification pipeline tools for transforming existing datasets into FAIR-compliant formats
- Natural language search and discovery service enabling users to find climate data using everyday language
- Multilingual question-answering system for climate adaptation knowledge
- Big data publishing pipeline service for making large climate datasets FAIR and accessible

Expected outputs: 10+ software tools

We will use open-source licenses, such as MIT and Apache 2.0, for the software developed in the project. A GitHub organization has been created to control the versioning of the software produced in the project.

The software will include comprehensive documentation with installation and usage guidelines to facilitate its deployment and replication in other projects and domains. We will follow the recommendations published by the project EVERSE⁴⁹.

To enhance their findability, we will create DOIs for each software project by uploading them to Zenodo using the GitHub-Zenodo bridge.

⁴⁹ <https://everse.software/RSQKit/>

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

To enhance their interoperability, we will use the Codemeta⁵⁰ specification to describe the software. This specification is compatible with Zenodo, it means, the software metadata will be propagated from Github to Zenodo automatically.

Model Configurations and Enhancements:

- Enhanced NorESM (Norwegian Earth System Model) configurations optimized for Arctic climate scenarios
- Modified CROCO model setups for coastal water quality assessment
- Containerized model environments ensuring reproducibility across different computing platforms
- Model metadata frameworks enabling better description and discovery of climate model outputs

Expected outputs: 3+ model configurations, containers (Dockerfile and other information to enable the creation of the corresponding singularity/docker containers);

Repository: Zenodo, institutional model repositories, Docker Hub (quay.io) for containers;

Access: Open access with usage documentation and example applications;

Community benefit: Reproducible climate modeling setups for Arctic and coastal research

Workflows and Methodologies

FAIRification Methodologies:

- Systematic workflows for transforming climate data from raw formats to FAIR Digital Objects
- Community engagement protocols for developing FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)
- Metadata enrichment workflows using AI and machine learning techniques
- Quality assessment and validation procedures for climate adaptation datasets
- Cross-community data integration methodologies

Expected outputs: Documented workflows, process guides

Repository: ROHub as Research Objects, and potentially workflow repositories such as WorkflowHub.eu;

Access: Open access with step-by-step implementation guides

Community benefit: Replicable processes for other climate adaptation initiatives.

Training and Capacity Building Resources:

- FAIR awareness training modules adapted for climate adaptation communities

⁵⁰ <https://codemeta.github.io/>

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

- Hands-on tutorials for using FAIR2Adapt tools and services
- Best practice guides for community-specific data management challenges
- Template documents for data management planning in climate adaptation projects
- Webinar series and recorded training sessions

Expected outputs: 25+ training resources, educational materials

Repository: Project website⁵¹, EOSC training platforms⁵², OSF⁵³, YouTube for videos⁵⁴

Access: Open access with Creative Commons licensing

Community benefit: Scalable training resources for global climate adaptation capacity building

Physical and Virtual Infrastructure

Dashboard and Visualization Templates:

- Customizable dashboard templates for publishing climate adaptation knowledge
- Interactive visualization tools for climate risk and vulnerability assessment
- Template applications for national adaptation hubs (based on Portuguese case study)
- Municipal climate data portal templates (based on Hamburg experience)
- Business climate risk assessment interfaces (aligned with EU Taxonomy requirements)

Expected outputs: 10+ dashboard templates, web applications;

Repository: GitHub repositories in the FAIR2Adapt Organisation⁵⁵, deployment on cloud platforms;

Access: Open source with customization documentation;

Community benefit: Ready-to-deploy solutions for adaptation planning organizations;

Knowledge Products and Frameworks:

- Climate adaptation taxonomies and knowledge graphs created through AI analysis
- Cross-cultural terminology mappings for multilingual climate adaptation
- Policy analysis frameworks linking scientific data with adaptation decision-making
- Integration guides for connecting FAIR2Adapt outputs with existing community platforms
- Evaluation frameworks for assessing FAIR data impact on adaptation planning

Expected outputs: 6+ knowledge frameworks, reference materials

⁵¹ <http://fair2adapt-eosc.eu>

⁵² <https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/catalogue/> and <https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/>

⁵³ <https://osf.io/>

⁵⁴ https://www.youtube.com/@FAIR2Adapt_EU-t5t

⁵⁵ <https://github.com/FAIR2Adapt>

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

Repository: ROHub, knowledge platforms (weADAPT, Connectivity Hub)

Access: Open access with attribution requirements

Community benefit: Structured knowledge resources for global adaptation community

Standards and Specifications

Metadata Schemas and Profiles:

- RO-Crate profiles specifically designed for climate adaptation resources
- Community-specific metadata schemas developed through Metadata for Machines (M4M) workshops
- Semantic interoperability profiles enabling cross-community data exchange
- API specifications for accessing and integrating FAIR2Adapt services
- Data quality standards and assessment criteria for climate adaptation datasets

Expected outputs: 12+ schemas and specifications

Repository: Schema registries, GitHub, standards documentation platforms

Access: Open access with version control and community feedback mechanisms

Community benefit: Reusable standards for climate adaptation data management globally

4. FAIR data

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Persistent Identifier Strategy

All datasets and research outputs will be assigned persistent identifiers according to a hierarchical system:

Primary Dataset Identifiers:

- DOIs for datasets deposited in repositories (Zenodo, NIRD Archive)
- PIDs for Research Objects in ROHub (W3ID)
- UUIDs for internal project data tracking during development

Supporting Identifiers:

- ORCID identifiers for all researchers and contributors
- ROR identifiers for all participating institutions
- URIs for vocabularies and metadata schemas developed in the project
- PIDs for software (DOIs) and workflow components

Comprehensive Metadata Framework

Rich metadata will be provided using a multi-layered approach combining general and domain-specific standards:

General Metadata Standards (Applied to All Data):

- Dublin Core for basic descriptive metadata (title, creator, subject, description, date, type, format, identifier, language, rights)
- DataCite schema for dataset citation and discovery
- DCAT-AP for data catalog interoperability across European portals
- RO-Crate for packaging and describing Research Object FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs)

Domain-Specific Metadata Standards:

- Climate and Forecast (CF) conventions for all climate model outputs and observational data
- INSPIRE metadata profiles for all geographic and environmental data
- STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog) for Earth observation and satellite data
- WMO Information System (WIS 2.0) standards for meteorological data

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- I-ADOPT framework for detailed variable descriptions and semantic alignment
- SeaDataNet standards for marine and coastal data
- ISO 19115/19139 for geographic information metadata

Community-Developed Metadata:

- RO-Crate profiles specifically designed for climate adaptation resources
- Community-specific schemas developed through Metadata for Machines (M4M) workshops
- Nanopublications for describing FAIR Supporting Resources and their relationships
- Custom vocabularies for climate adaptation concepts not covered by existing standards will be developed through the case study communities via Metadata for Machines (M4M) workshops.

Search Optimization and Controlled Vocabularies

Search keywords will be provided using established and custom vocabularies:

International Vocabularies:

- Climate Change Knowledge Portal terms for climate concepts
- GEMET (General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus) for environmental terms
- NASA GCMD Science Keywords for Earth science disciplines
- NERC vocabularies for marine, atmospheric, and climate data
- INSPIRE themes for geographic and environmental categories

Project-Developed Vocabularies:

- Custom climate adaptation taxonomies developed through AI analysis of community content
- Cross-cultural terminology mappings for multilingual accessibility
- Business-oriented climate risk vocabularies aligned with EU Taxonomy requirements
- Urban climate adaptation terms specific to municipal planning needs

Metadata Harvesting and Indexing Strategy

Metadata will be made harvestable and indexed through multiple channels:

Standard Protocols:

- OAI-PMH protocols from all participating repositories
- SPARQL endpoints for linked data access

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- REST APIs from ROHub and other FAIR2Adapt platforms
- OpenAIRE Research Graph integration for European research discoverability

EOSC Integration:

- EOSC Portal metadata aggregation;
- Integration with EOSC Federation services for search and discovery;
- Compliance with EOSC Interoperability Framework guidelines;

Community Platforms:

- Integration with Climate-ADAPT metadata systems
- weADAPT platform search optimization
- Municipal data portal indexing (Hamburg, Portugal)
- Business climate data platform integration

4.2. Making data accessible

Data will be deposited in repositories that support FAIR data. Primary repositories include:

Institutional Repositories:

- Norwegian Research Data Archive (NIRD) - CoreTrustSeal certified
- Zenodo - CERN-operated, OpenAIRE compliant
- ROHub - EOSC service for Research Objects

Domain-Specific Repositories:

- PANGAEA for Earth system data
- Climate Data Store (Copernicus C3S)
- Marine Data repositories (JERICO-RI network)

Platform-Specific:

- Hamburg Urban Data Platform
- weADAPT knowledge platform
- EGI DataHub (EOSC federated)

All repositories provide:

- Persistent identifier assignment
- Long-term preservation commitments

D1.2 – Data Management Plan

- Standardized metadata schemas
- Open access capabilities

Most data will be openly available, following "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" principle.

Data Access Levels and Justification

Open Access Data (approximately 85% of project data):

- All climate model outputs and derived indicators
- Research software, workflows, and analysis notebooks
- Aggregated socio-economic indicators (anonymized)
- Policy-relevant summaries and visualizations
- Educational and training materials

Controlled Access Data (approximately 10% of project data):

- High-resolution socio-economic data requiring privacy protection
- Detailed infrastructure vulnerability assessments with security implications
- Business-specific climate risk data under commercial confidentiality agreements

Restricted Access Data (approximately 5% of project data):

- Personal or household-level data that cannot be anonymized
- Data under third-party licensing restrictions that prevent redistribution
- Security-sensitive infrastructure data requiring authorization

Access Mechanisms and Timeline

Immediate Access (upon publication):

- All open access datasets available immediately upon deposit
- Research Objects with complete metadata and documentation
- Software and workflows with installation and usage instructions

Controlled Access Procedures:

- Data access committees established for sensitive datasets
- Clear application procedures with response time commitments (maximum 30 days)
- User authentication through institutional or ORCID credentials

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- Usage agreements specifying permitted uses and attribution requirements

Embargo Policies

Limited embargoes will apply only in specific circumstances:

- Maximum 12-month embargo for datasets supporting publications under review
- No embargo for datasets required for regulatory compliance (EU Taxonomy data)
- Early access for project partners and case study stakeholders during development phase
- Public access prioritized for all policy-relevant datasets

Data will be made accessible through standard protocols:

- HTTPS for web-based access
- OPeNDAP for climate data subsetting
- OGC WMS/WFS for geospatial data
- SPARQL for linked data queries
- FTP/GridFTP for large file transfers

4.3. Making data interoperable

File Format Standards and Justification

FAIR2Adapt will use established, community-endorsed file formats to ensure maximum interoperability across climate adaptation communities:

Climate and Environmental Data:

- NetCDF-4 with CF (Climate and Forecast) conventions for climate model outputs and observational data - chosen for broad community adoption and self-describing metadata capabilities
- Zarr format for cloud-optimized access to large multidimensional arrays - enables efficient access to large datasets like NorESM and CROCO model outputs
- HDF5 for complex hierarchical scientific datasets requiring high performance access

Geospatial Data:

- GeoJSON-LD for vector geographic data with semantic annotations - provides web compatibility while supporting linked data principles

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- GeoTIFF with embedded coordinate reference systems for raster geographic data
- Shapefiles for compatibility with existing GIS systems and municipal data platforms like Hamburg's Geoportal

Research Objects and Metadata:

- RO-Crate for research object packaging - chosen as the primary FDO implementation format for FAIR2Adapt
- JSON-LD for structured metadata with semantic web compatibility

Vocabulary Standards and Semantic Framework

Established International Vocabularies:

- I-ADOPT framework for standardized description of observable variables and their measurement contexts
- Climate Change Knowledge Portal vocabularies for climate science concepts
- GEMET (General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus) for environmental terminology
- NERC vocabularies for marine, atmospheric, and climate data
- NASA GCMD Science Keywords for Earth science disciplines

Project and Community-Developed Vocabularies:

- Custom climate adaptation taxonomies developed through AI analysis of community content (Case Study 5)
- Cross-cultural terminology mappings for multilingual accessibility
- Business-oriented climate risk vocabularies aligned with EU Taxonomy requirements (Case Study 6)
- Municipal adaptation planning vocabularies for urban climate services (Case Study 3)

Interoperability Framework Implementation

FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs): Each case study community will develop FIPs that collectively decide which FAIR Supporting Resources such as vocabularies and metadata schemas should be used within the community. This includes:

- Community-specific metadata schemas developed through Metadata for Machines (M4M) workshops
- Recommended repositories and platforms for data sharing
- Quality assessment criteria and validation procedures

D1.2 – Data Management Plan

- Community-specific best practices for data citation and attribution

Semantic Interoperability Profiles (SIPs): Complementing FIPs, SIPs will define semantic mappings between different vocabulary systems used by communities, ensuring cross-community data integration and automated reasoning capabilities for data discovery.

EOSC Interoperability Framework Compliance:

- Technical interoperability through standardized APIs and data formats
- Semantic interoperability via controlled vocabularies and ontologies
- Organizational interoperability through community governance structures
- Legal interoperability via clear licensing and usage agreements

Cross-Reference and Mapping Strategies

Automated Mapping Services:

- Automated I-ADOPT service for aligning dataset variables across different communities
- SSSOM (Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings) for vocabulary mappings published in the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
- Machine learning techniques for crosswalks between metadata schemas
- API-based integration between different repository systems

Manual Expert Curation:

- Domain expert validation of automated mappings for complex climate adaptation concepts
- Community workshops to establish consensus on terminology usage
- Peer review processes for new vocabulary terms and mappings

Target Ontologies and Standards Alignment:

- Wikidata for general concepts and geographic entities
- ENVO (Environmental Ontology) for environmental features and processes
- SWEET (Semantic Web for Earth and Environmental Terminology) for Earth science concepts
- Climate domain ontologies for specialized adaptation concepts

Qualified References and Data Linking

Data will include qualified references to other data through multiple mechanisms:

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

Internal Project Relationships:

- DOI citations to related datasets within FAIR2Adapt case studies
- Provenance chains using PROV-O vocabulary to document data transformations and processing steps
- Research Object links in RO-Crates connecting datasets, software, workflows, and publications
- Cross-references in nanopublications describing FAIR Supporting Resources

External Data Integration:

- Semantic links between variables using I-ADOPT framework for cross-dataset variable alignment
- Citations to source datasets from external repositories and climate data platforms
- Links to related research through OpenAIRE Research Graph integration
- Connections to policy documents and regulatory frameworks (EU Taxonomy, national adaptation strategies)

Community Standards Adoption and Extension

The project follows established community practices while extending them for climate adaptation needs:

Existing Standards Compliance:

- CF conventions for climate data metadata and variable descriptions
- INSPIRE directive requirements for geographic information in European context
- WIS 2.0 and WIGOS standards for meteorological data exchange
- OGC standards for geospatial web services and data access

FAIR2Adapt Extensions:

- RO-Crate profiles specifically developed for climate adaptation resources
- Enhanced metadata schemas for policy and governance data
- Custom STAC extensions for multi-temporal climate analysis
- Community-endorsed vocabularies for adaptation planning concepts

Community Validation and Engagement:

- Regular community feedback sessions on standards usage through case study stakeholder groups
- Collaborative development of best practice guidelines via M4M workshops

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- Integration with existing community data management workflows
- Training and capacity building for FAIR standards adoption across all case studies

4.4. Increase data re-use

Documentation Strategy for Validation and Re-use

FAIR2Adapt will provide comprehensive documentation to facilitate data validation and re-use across climate adaptation communities:

Methodology and Context Documentation:

- README files with detailed methodology descriptions, variable definitions, units of measurement, and data collection procedures
- Codebooks explaining data cleaning processes, quality control measures, and any transformations applied
- Data lineage documentation tracing datasets from original sources through all processing steps
- Uncertainty quantification and quality indicators for model outputs and derived products

Interactive Documentation and Examples:

- Jupyter notebooks demonstrating data usage patterns, analysis workflows, and visualization techniques
- API documentation with code examples in Python, R, and other commonly used languages
- Video tutorials and webinars showcasing how to access and work with specific datasets
- Step-by-step guides for integrating FAIR2Adapt data with existing community tools and workflows

Community-Specific Guidance:

- Best practice guides tailored to each case study community's needs and technical capabilities
- HOWTOs for common tasks like data extraction, downscaling, merging datasets from various sources
- Template scripts for computing climate risk and vulnerability indices
- Integration guides for popular tools like QGIS, Excel, and domain-specific software platforms

Licensing Strategy for Maximum Re-use

FAIR2Adapt adopts a tiered licensing approach to maximize re-use while respecting data constraints:

Open Access Data (approximately 85% of project data):

- CC0 (Public Domain Dedication) for factual climate datasets, observational data, and model outputs
- CC BY 4.0 (Attribution) for derived products, visualizations, analysis results, and educational materials

Software and Computational Resources:

- Open source licenses (MIT, Apache 2.0, GPL-3.0) for all project-developed software and tools
- Container images and workflows shared under permissive licenses enabling modification and redistribution
- Documentation and training materials under CC BY to encourage adaptation and translation

Restricted Access Data:

- Custom license agreements for controlled access data specifying permitted uses, attribution requirements, and redistribution limitations
- Clear terms of use for business-sensitive data that enable research while protecting commercial interests
- Data use agreements for sensitive socio-economic data ensuring privacy protection and ethical use

Third-Party Usability and Sustainability Measures

Post-Project Accessibility:

- Deposit in long-term preservation repositories with guaranteed minimum 10-year accessibility commitments
- Clear preservation commitments from repository providers including backup strategies and disaster recovery
- Migration pathways documented for evolving data formats and technological changes

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

- Integration with ongoing infrastructure services (EOSC, national research infrastructures) for sustained access

Technology Evolution Strategies:

- Technology migration strategies for obsolete formats including automatic format conversion where possible
- Version control systems maintaining historical versions while enabling format updates
- Community adoption strategies ensuring standards and tools continue beyond project completion
- Integration with established research infrastructures and operational climate services

Community Sustainability:

- Training programs for case study communities to maintain and extend datasets independently
- Documentation of data management procedures enabling communities to continue FAIRification practices
- Collaboration agreements with long-term data providers ensuring continued data availability
- Integration with institutional data management systems for sustained community support

Provenance Documentation and Transparency

Comprehensive provenance will be documented using established standards:

Data Lineage Documentation:

- PROV-O (Provenance Ontology) standard for machine-readable provenance information
- Complete data lineage from original sources through all processing steps to final products
- Processing workflow documentation including software versions, parameters, and computational environments
- Quality control and validation step documentation with timestamps and responsible parties

Attribution and Credit:

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- Author and contributor attribution for all datasets and derived products
- Institutional affiliations and funding source acknowledgments
- Clear citation requirements and suggested citation formats for all data products
- ORCID identifiers for all contributors enabling proper academic credit

Technical Provenance:

- Software tool versions and parameter settings used in data processing
- Computational environment specifications including operating systems and library versions
- Hardware specifications for model runs and data processing tasks
- Checksums and digital signatures for data integrity verification

Quality Assurance and Validation Processes

Multi-Level Quality Control:

- Automated quality checks during the FAIRification process including format validation and metadata completeness
- Expert validation by domain specialists within each case study community
- Peer review processes for datasets supporting scientific publications
- Community feedback mechanisms through case study stakeholder groups

Continuous Quality Monitoring:

- Version control and change tracking for all datasets with clear versioning policies
- Regular quality assessments using FAIR evaluation metrics adapted for climate adaptation data
- User feedback integration for improving data quality and documentation
- Error reporting and correction procedures with transparent update processes

Validation Support for Re-users:

- Validation datasets and test cases for verifying correct data usage
- Benchmark results and expected outcomes for common analysis tasks
- Uncertainty estimates and confidence intervals for model outputs and derived indicators
- Comparison datasets enabling users to validate their analysis approaches

Enhanced Re-use Through FAIR Digital Objects

FDO-Enabled Data Integration:

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

- Research Objects (RO-Crates) packaging datasets with all necessary context and documentation
- Persistent identifiers enabling reliable citation and long-term access
- Semantic annotations facilitating automated discovery and integration
- Executable workflows packaged with data enabling reproducible analysis

Cross-Community Integration:

- Standardized variable descriptions using I-ADOPT framework enabling automatic alignment between datasets
- Semantic mappings between community vocabularies facilitating cross-domain research
- API access enabling programmatic integration with external tools and platforms
- Interoperable metadata formats supporting automated harvesting and indexing

User-Friendly Access Mechanisms:

- Natural language query interfaces for non-technical users to discover relevant data
- Dashboard templates enabling stakeholders to create customized visualizations
- Integration with popular analysis platforms (Jupyter, R, QGIS, Excel) through dedicated packages
- Multi-lingual interfaces and documentation supporting global climate adaptation communities

5. Allocation of resources

In FAIR2Adapt, resource allocation refers to the planning and funding required to make research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). These costs vary depending on the type and volume of data generated, including model outputs, derived products (e.g. from data fusion), and socio-economic data, across case studies and transfer cases.

Resource Planning and Cost Distribution

D1.2 – Data Management PLaN

Data management costs within FAIR2Adapt are distributed across work packages according to their specific data responsibilities: WP2 and WP3 handle the technical infrastructure and FAIRification processes, WP5 covers community training and engagement in FAIR practices, WP6 manages case study data collection and processing, and WP7 addresses data-related communication and dissemination needs. This distributed approach ensures that data management activities are integrated throughout the project rather than treated as separate overhead costs.

FAIR2Adapt leverages access to FAIR-enabling services and infrastructures, including those provided through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For example, services such as ROHub for managing Research Objects, the FAIR Implementation Profile Wizard (FIP Wizard), and FAIR DMP Wizard for Data Management Plans (DMPs) are key to supporting FAIR data practices. In addition, FAIR2Adapt makes use of computational infrastructures to support data processing and analysis, including EGI Jupyter Notebooks, Pangeo@EOSC, and the Galaxy Europe platform. For AI-driven services such as automated taxonomy construction, multilingual question answering, and metadata extraction, the project is exploring the use of AI4EOSC infrastructure to deploy and serve machine learning models, though long-term sustainability of AI model hosting beyond the project duration remains under evaluation. The project also integrates with community-specific platforms relevant to climate change adaptation, such as weADAPT, the Connectivity Hub, and local platforms like the Hamburg Urban Data and Modelling Platforms, to ensure alignment with the needs of both scientific and policy stakeholders. Furthermore, the project ensures the storage of large datasets, which will be made available via EOSC storage services (EGI datahub) and other trusted repositories (Norwegian Research Data Archive), ensuring compliance with FAIR principles and supporting long-term data accessibility. Costs related to the use of these services, infrastructures, and storage are either covered free of charge or planned under the project's work packages, particularly those related to FAIRification, case study development, and scaling of transfer cases.

Governance and Decision-Making Framework

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

Simula, as project coordinator, plays a central role in overseeing data management and coordinating FAIR practices across the consortium. However, each partner is responsible for the FAIR handling of the data they generate or curate, including identifying any specific constraints or access limitations (e.g. due to privacy or licensing). Repository selection decisions are made jointly between data-generating partners and relevant case study communities, with technical validation by the project's data management team. Quality control procedures involve both automated validation during FAIRification and expert review by domain specialists within each case study community. The implementation of FAIR and CARE principles is especially important when handling sensitive socio-economic data, ensuring anonymization and aggregation where necessary.

Major data management activities are scheduled throughout the project timeline: initial data inventory and assessment (months 1-6), community engagement and FIP development (months 3-18), intensive FAIRification implementation (months 6-30), and final validation and preservation (months 24-36). This phased approach ensures adequate resource allocation while allowing for iterative improvement based on community feedback.

Long-term Sustainability and Preservation

For long-term preservation, data and associated outputs will be managed as Research Objects in ROHub, which provides sustainability mechanisms, including quality tracking. Where appropriate, datasets will be deposited in trusted domain-specific or institutional repositories, such as the NIRD Research Data Archive, Zenodo, or other relevant archives, that support FAIR principles and ensure long-term availability. Each data provider will ensure their chosen repository aligns with FAIR principles and provides necessary guarantees for preservation.

Sustainability resource planning minimizes long-term preservation costs through selection of repositories with institutional sustainability commitments and proven track records. Post-project maintenance of FAIR2Adapt tools and services will be transitioned to appropriate community organizations and research infrastructures based on demonstrated adoption and value. This approach ensures continued availability of project outputs while avoiding unsustainable maintenance burdens on individual partners.

Access to project data and outputs will be free of charge to users, ensuring that the FAIR2Adapt results can be widely reused and integrated into broader climate adaptation knowledge systems.

6. Security and Ethics considerations

D1.2 – Data Management PPlan

FAIR2Adapt will work with data collected from existing sources and will also generate new data through model outputs and derived products, including results from data fusion processes. In cases where socio-economic or potentially sensitive data is processed, the project will apply robust anonymisation techniques. Particular attention will be given to ensure that no individual can be identified—for example, by aggregating data over larger geographic units and avoiding resolution that could reveal personal or household-level details.

All data handling will be performed in compliance with relevant data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as applicable. While FAIR2Adapt does not anticipate processing sensitive personal data as a core activity, procedures will be in place to ensure that any data with potential privacy concerns is managed appropriately. This includes the use of metadata that clearly indicates licensing, provenance, and anonymisation status.

Simula, the project coordinator, is responsible for data protection compliance. The Data Protection Officer (DPO) can be contacted at:

Data Protection Officer

Simula Research Laboratory

Email: dpo@simula.no

In addition to adhering to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), the project is committed to upholding the CARE principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) in managing and sharing data, particularly where data concerns Indigenous communities or local knowledge.

From a security standpoint, FAIR2Adapt will ensure that access to internal project data during the project lifetime is strictly managed through secure platforms. Internal collaboration and data sharing will take place using Google Workspace services provided and administered by Simula, ensuring compliance with institutional security policies. Access to shared documents and folders will be restricted based on roles, with appropriate authentication and access control measures in place.

Secure data repositories aligned with EOSC services will be used for long-term storage and open access, with integrity checks and metadata validation procedures in place to avoid data tampering or loss.

7. Annex

We use <https://fip.fair-wizard.com/> to create an online, machine-actionable detailed Data Management Plan (DMP) for FAIR2Adapt. The current FAIR2Adapt DMP questionnaire and its corresponding answers are publicly available at:

<https://fip.fair-wizard.com/wizard/projects/7d647ed2-6698-4be3-ac81-502329066b3c>.

As the DMP evolves with the project, we took a snapshot on June 29th 2025. This snapshot version is available at:

<https://w3id.org/ro-id/5954ce8e-2bbc-469a-b5ba-0d4d1e93195f/resources/f152dc94-e6c8-4232-b301-951ce2fc37f2>